

Optimization of a Sail-Shaped Façade Structure of a Multi-Storey Office Building

F. Maden¹, E. Yıldırım^{1*}, D. Ölmez¹, A. Couvelas²

¹Department of Architecture, Yaşar University
 Üniversite Cad., No:37-39, Ağaçlı Yol, 35100 Bornova, İzmir, Turkey
 feray.maden@yasar.edu.tr, erinc.yildirim@yasar.edu.tr, duhan.olmez@yasar.edu.tr

²COUVELAS/KOUVELAS Architects
 agnes@couvelas.net

ABSTRACT

Human population on world is increasing drastically and uncontrolled way. This increase in population requires us re-think how we use resources. As a result of this, many researches come up in different disciplines about reducing the usage of resources to provide sustainable solutions of their discipline related problems. In architectural discipline, these studies not only aim to reduce material but also energy usage of the building since the building and construction related sectors are using 41.1% of the global produced energy. The share of energy consumption was 33.7% due to the population growth and people spend 90% of their lives indoor spaces which requires to be mechanically ventilated and air conditioned.

In this study, a multi-storey office building located in Athens is selected. The office building consists of four floors with west facing glazing façade that negatively affects the energy performance of the building and decrease the indoor quality by creating glare and overheating problems.

This study focuses on controlling daylight prevent glares and possible overheating of the office space by optimizing external hybrid shading devices geometries to increase the average useful daylight index while maximizing visual perception by genetic algorithm based heuristic approach.

Daylight model is created in Rhinoceros® modelling software Daylight calculations are done in radiance with the help of Ladybug and Honeybee plug-in of Grasshopper® parametric modelling plug-in of Rhinoceros®. For the optimization of the shading device geometry, OCTOPUS plug-in utilized for its ability to optimize multi-objective problems.

The result of the study shows that optimization of the external shading device affects the daylight performance and reduces the required energy for cooling the building during the summer period while satisfying the visual connection between indoor and outdoor. Not only a single solution for the problem but also some design alternatives are obtained due to the utilizing multi objective optimization method.

